

OFDM Wideband DOA System for Detecting and Tracking Vehicles Applications

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Abstract— This work proposes a new angle of arrival method for tracking applications using compact omni-directional spiral antenna arrays. The impact of mutual coupling is considered within the covariance matrix calculation and then a suitable decoupling method is used to remove such effect. An urban area consisting of many buildings with different heights and characterized by various materials was modelled using Wireless In-Site Software to extract the impulse response of the channel between non-stationary locations of the transmitted target and the receiver antenna array. Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) scheme based on wideband spectrum is integrated with the proposed angle of arrival to improve the estimation accuracy. MATLAB code is developed to simulate the above conditions and the experiment results are presented and discussed.

Index Terms— antenna array, tracking systems, propagation, multipath channel, OFDM, DOA and location estimation, localisation, wireless communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Position-awareness is currently an active research topic playing a fundamental role in many applications including tracking systems [1], rescue-and-search operations [2] and localisation services in fifth generation (5G) cellular networks [3]. Although the Global Positioning System (GPS) is efficient technology that can provide accurate position-awareness around the world through a constellation of at least twenty four satellites [4], the efficiency of GPS drops in harsh environments, for example, in urban canyons, in caves and buildings and under tree canopies [5], since most GPS signals are not able to penetrate obstacles. Therefore, new and more accurate localisation techniques are needed for use in such environments. A wideband wireless network can provide precise localisation in GPS-denied environments [6]. In particular, wide bandwidth signals can provide reliable and accurate range measurements due to their fine delay precision and robustness in harsh environments [7]. In general, position-aware networks consist of two categories of nodes: anchors and agents. The location of anchors can be known through system design or GPS, whereas the agent's positions are initially unknown and attempt to find their locations. In order to determine its position and/or directions, each node needs to be equipped with a wideband transceiver, and localisation can be achieved through radio signaling between users and their neighbouring anchors. Localising a target needs a number of signals sent from the anchors, and the relative location of the target can be inferred from these incoming signals using a variety of waveforms metrics. Due to possible physical obstructions in the direct path, non-line-

of-sight (NLOS) conditions can result, together with multiple paths, resulting in fading and interference issues.

Angle of Arrival (AOA) is a popular approach in which the arrival angles of the agents, which arrive to the base stations are used to estimate a target's location [8]. Wideband AOA systems can estimate not only the LOS direction of emitters but also the direction of multipath components, which provide extra spatial information. However, since the received signals are affected by random phenomena, for instance fading, scattering, shadowing, NLOS and multipath propagation, the estimation of an agent's location can be uncertain. In the state of the art, comparatively few works have investigated the impact of NLOS and multipath propagations on localisation resolution. Other studies utilize narrowband signal models, which use averaging of the received path and are not applicable for wideband networks. In contrast, wideband AOA models utilize the directions of all the multiple paths, which have different directions, timings and signal strengths.

The size of an antenna array is crucial in several applications and should be as small as is practical. Typically, it is most desirable for localization and tracking systems to combine an efficient angle of arrival technique with small compact omni-directional antenna arrays. The contribution of this work is to integrate the compact omni-directional spiral antenna that proposed in [9] with a new, efficient AOA algorithm for tracking applications in urban areas. This system is intended to work on top of cars, so that the smallest antenna height is desirable. An urban area is modelled in Wireless-Insite software where NLOS and multipath propagations are produced and then used to track and localise the agent's position. The mutual coupling matrix is calculated as in [10] and then inserted in the covariance matrix, when an appropriate decoupling algorithm eliminates the effect of mutual coupling. The OFDM scheme is used in this study to combat multipath phenomenon, with the received signals split into many small narrowband sub-carriers to improve the estimation accuracy. Several estimation strategies are investigated such as exploiting the strongest signal path, the path with least time of arrival, and the averaging of all or some of the arrival path.

The rest of this paper is organized as following. Section II provides the mathematical model for the antenna array and the OFDM scheme to be used. In section III, the principles and mathematical model of a new algorithm we call "Inverse of Subtracting" (IOS) are presented. The computer

simulation, experimental results and discussions appear in section IV. Section V summarizes the results and gives brief conclusions.

II. ANTENNA ARRAY AND SIGNAL MODELLING WITH OFDM

A circular array of spiral antennas is a common geometry which can be used to increase gain. It is suitable in scenarios where 360 degrees of coverage or both elevation and azimuth for specific coverage area are required. For a resonant frequency of 400 MHz, the geometry of the antenna array used in this work is shown in Fig.1. The radius (r) of the ring array is calculated based on ($d = \lambda/2 = 37.5$ cm), then $r = r = \frac{d}{2 \sin(\frac{\pi}{M})} = 31.9$ cm, where M is the number of antenna elements.

Fig. 1: Basic geometry of 5 element spiral antenna array on finite ground plane.

After the antenna array receives all signals from different directions of arrival (DOA)s, the OFDM scheme is applied to divide the active transmission bandwidth into narrow band carriers which are suitable for wideband AOA estimation. The broadband impulse channel response is given by:

$$h(\tau) = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k e^{j\phi_k} \delta(\tau - \tau_k) \quad (1)$$

Apply an input signal:

$$f(t, \omega) = e^{j\omega t} \quad (2)$$

Then the output can be simplified to the following:

$$s(t, \omega) = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k e^{j\phi_k} e^{j\omega(t - \tau_k)} \quad (3)$$

This alternatively can be given by:

$$s(t, \omega) = e^{j\omega t} \sum_{k=1}^n a_k e^{j\phi_k} e^{-j\omega \tau_k} = e^{j\omega t} U(\omega) \quad (4)$$

Extending $U(\omega)$ over baseband bandwidth B (as shown in Fig.2) for N frequency samples, then the i^{th} frequency sample can be expressed by:

$$f_i = -\frac{B}{2} + (i-1)N\Delta f \quad (5)$$

$$f_i = -\frac{B}{2} + (i-1)n\frac{B}{N} = \frac{B}{2}(-1 + (i-1)\frac{2n}{N})$$

where

$$N\Delta f = B \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2: Assumed bandwidth range

The sampling time can be stated as follows:

$$\frac{1}{2\Delta t} = \frac{B}{2}, \text{ hence } \Delta t = \frac{1}{B} \quad (7)$$

Thus, the minimum sampling frequency is:

$$f_s \geq 2\frac{B}{2} = B \quad (8)$$

The i^{th} uniform frequency sample of $U(\omega)$ can be given by:

$$U(2\pi f_i) = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k e^{j\phi_k} e^{-j\omega \tau_k} e^{-j2\pi f_i \tau_k} \quad (9)$$

Then, the covariance matrix is computed as follows:

$$R_{xx} = U U^H \quad (10)$$

III. THE MAXIMUM SIGNAL SUBSPACE (MSS) AOA METHOD

After the covariance matrix is obtained, an AOA is applied method to estimate DOAs. The proposed algorithm is based on the orthogonality between manifold array vector and the eigenvector associated with the largest eigenvalue with regressed less to the number of received signals. Therefore, the new method does not require previous knowledge of the number of arrival signals in comparison with Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) [11] and Estimation of Signal Parameters via Rotational Invariance Technique (ESPRIT) [12]. To summarise the proposed algorithm, first we construct the covariance matrix (R_{xx}), secondly apply eigenvalue decomposition (EVD) on R_{xx} to yield:

$$R_{xx} = Q \Sigma Q^H \quad (11)$$

Q is the ($M \times M$) eigenvectors matrix and is given as follows:

$$Q = [q_1, q_2, \dots, q_M] \quad (12)$$

and Σ are the eigenvalues that corresponding to every eigenvector, given by:

$$\Sigma = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_M] \quad (13)$$

Next sort the eigenvalues in descending order (i.e. $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2 > \lambda_3 > \dots > \lambda_M$) and choose the eigenvector associated with the largest eigenvalue (λ_1). Once this eigenvector is obtained, the spatial spectrum can be constructed by using the following equation:

$$P_1(\theta) = q_1 a(\theta) \quad (14)$$

Then, normalise the pseudospectrum of the above equation using the maximum value:

$$P_{Norm}(\theta) = P_1(\theta) / \max(P_1(\theta)) \quad (15)$$

Next subtract $P_{Norm}(\theta)$ from unity in order to obtain narrower peaks and also to minimize side-lobe levels, as described below:

$$P_S(\theta) = 1 - P_{Norm} \quad (16)$$

Once this condition is achieved, we will obtain nulls in the direction of received signals, to obtain peaks in the DOA signals, the inverse of subtracting (IOS) is computed as follows:

$$P_{Ios}(\theta) = \frac{1}{P_S(\theta) + \varepsilon} \quad (17)$$

where ε is a small scalar value added in order to avoid possible singularities. The last step is find the locations of the peaks to determine the direction of the transmitters or targets.

Fig. 3. Showing scenario of tracking process for an outdoor urban area.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we simulate the proposed system for tracking scenario such as rescue-and-search operations and /or public security applications. A 5-element spiral antenna array is located on top of a vehicle at 2 m height. These sensors are spatially distributed in the azimuthal plane with angular separation of 72 degrees and inter-element spacing set to $\lambda/2$. The wireless propagation simulation software Wireless Insite is used in this study since it can provide the most realistic simulation model for wireless propagation. It is an electromagnetic simulation tool that helps predict the propagation behaviour of electromagnetic waves in the presence of objects with different electrical properties. The tracking scenario used in this work is an urban environment (1000 m \times 650 m): part of this area is shown in Fig. 3. An omni-directional transmitter antenna located at a height of 1.5 m was considered for the evaluation process.

The urban area consists of many buildings with different heights, with a maximum height of 50 m. There are various materials - concrete, brick and wet earth. The loudest received path is only shown in Fig. 3 to avoid ambiguity in the

presence of so much multipath. As can be seen in Fig.3, the tracking process is started by taking the first measurement at point Rx1-1 and then at point Rx2-1, ... until the last point at Rx8-1. The sequence and location of the receiver at these points and of the transmitter are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Showing the sequence and location of the receiver at each point in the tracking process.

Tracking steps sequences	Location of receiver in x(m)	Location of receiver in y (m)
a. Rx1-1	994	297
b. Rx2-1	928	292
c. Rx3-1	859	290
d. Rx4-1	849	250
e. Rx5-1	847	180
f. Rx6-1	767	172
g. Rx7-1	765	131
h. Rx8-1	753	89
i. Tx1	720	59

At each point of the tracking process, the antenna array receives ten multipath at each element with different power, TOA and phase. The impulse response from all received channels between non-stationary locations of the transmitted target and the receiver antenna is processed via the wideband OFDM scheme: the bandwidth here is 10 MHz, split over 64 sub-carriers. The IFFT was applied to the received channel transfer function to acquire the impulse response with 10 multipaths. Based on the suggested bandwidth the tracking process was applied over several options such as loudest signal strength, least time of arrival and the average of all / or small number of arrival paths.

The covariance matrix is calculated and the effect of the mutual coupling is taken into account, and an appropriate decoupling method is exploited to reduce the coupling effects. Then the data are passed to the IOS angle of arrival method to estimate DOAs and track the location of the agent. This process is repeated at each measurement point in Table 1 and the estimated direction at each point is shown in Fig.4. The performance estimation of the proposed system can be presented based on the locations of receiver at all the measurement points and the estimated directions at these points as shown in Fig.5. As can be seen from this graph, the proposed system works efficiently and it is useful for such applications. Another advantages has been obtained in the IOS algorithm is by removing the false peaks and/or the side lobe issues completely, which otherwise could create uncertainty for selecting the correct direction.

negative effects from the covariance matrix. An example was implemented to simulate the scenario of tracking in an urban area under multipath conditions and the results confirmed that the proposed tracking system works efficiently.

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V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new and efficient angle of arrival method has been presented based on the received signals from a 5-element ring array for outdoor tracking, using small omnidirectional spiral antennas for possible integration on top of cars. OFDM over a wideband spectrum was considered and found to be suitable modulation candidate for a such tracking system. The mutual coupling effect was included and an efficient decoupling method was utilized to eliminate the